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Sub-optical-cycle electron pulse trains from metal nanotips

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Abstract

The coherent modulation of swift electron beams with strong laser fields has enabled the generation of attosecond electron pulses, opening up new research avenues in ultrafast science. Here we study a comparatively simple alternative, the production of electron pulse trains directly at the source. In our theory work, we show that sub-optical-cycle electron bursts induced by tunneling photoemission from a metal nanotip can retain the temporal fingerprint of their emission dynamics in a typical low-energy point-projection microscope setup. We find that strong acceleration by a static field, a short propagation distance and a sufficiently large optical cycle duration mitigate temporal smearing due to matter-wave dispersion. Our approach enables studies of coherent interactions of slow electrons with matter on sub-femtosecond and nanometer scales, a regime which has hitherto remained inaccessible.

Keywords: attosecond, nanotips, photoemission

(Some figures may appear in colour only in the online journal)

1. Introduction

Attosecond science is a rapidly advancing field of research studying ultrafast dynamics in a wide range of systems, such as atoms, molecules and solids [1]. The sub-optical-cycle interaction of strong laser fields with electrons initially bound inside these systems are at the heart of attosecond science, most prominently producing attosecond light bursts (see [2] for a review). In recent years, studies of the interaction of free electron beams with strong laser fields [3–6] and the generation of attosecond electron pulses [7–10] have opened up a new perspective for attosecond science. It is well known that swift electron beams carry highly localized white-light electric fields and can exchange energy with nanophotonic structures and quantum emitters with nanometer spatial resolution, while lacking time resolution [11, 12]. In contrast, an electron beam composed of a train of attosecond electron pulses opens up

studies of attosecond charge dynamics, electromagnetic waveforms [10], nano-optical excitations [13], coherent control of quantum systems [14], sub- and super-radiant light emission [15] and quantum coherence in materials [16], only to name a few.

Several approaches enable the generation of attosecond electron pulse trains. In photon-induced near-field electron microscopy (PINEM), a pulsed electron beam interacts with a strongly localized optical near-field inside a transmission electron microscopy (TEM) [3]. A comb of sidebands appears in the energy spectrum, corresponding to the absorption and emission of multiple photons from the light field. In a groundbreaking study, Feist *et al* demonstrated that PINEM imprints a coherent phase modulation on an femtosecond electron pulse under optimal conditions [6]. Because the faster electrons catch up with the slower electrons in the energy comb, an attosecond electron pulse train is formed downstream at a certain drift distance from the interaction region between near-field and electron pulse. This prediction has been confirmed in later experiments [7, 8]. PINEM has also been demonstrated in a scanning electron microscope (SEM) setting [17] and is feasible even for low-energy electron beams below

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Figure 1. PPM setup. (a) A femtosecond laser pulse (red) irradiates a metal nanotip. The optical near-field at the apex leads to the emission of an electron pulse train (blue), which travels to the sample plane. A distant screen (not shown) records the point-projection image corresponding to the electron–sample interaction. (b) Local near-field enhancement (red curve) and static tip-sample potential (black curve) as a function of the distance z from the metal–vacuum interface.

500 eV [18, 19]. Besides PINEM, several other approaches can produce attosecond electron pulses, such as acceleration at membrane interfaces [10, 20], dielectric laser acceleration [9] and free-space ponderomotive electron acceleration [21, 22]. The required drift distance for the appearance of attosecond pulse trains is in the micrometer to millimeter range, depending on the interaction parameters and the beam energy [6, 8–10, 22]. The spatial range for retaining the attosecond pulse trains upon further propagation of the electrons corresponds to a fraction of the drift distance. At larger distances, the pulse train disperses and the bunching disappears [6]. All approaches described here have in common that they are based on the downstream manipulation of free-space femtosecond electron pulses emitted from a laser-triggered electron source.

In our theory study, we investigate the generation of attosecond electron pulses directly at the electron source and its potential application for electron–light–matter interactions within a practical point-projection microscope (PPM) setup. Our approach is based on the fact that the strong-field tunneling photoemission from metallic emitters can be confined to sub-optical-cycle durations in the attosecond and femtosecond regimes [23, 24]. Specifically, metal nanotips and other metal nanostructures triggered by femtosecond laser pulses in the near- and mid-infrared emit sub-optical-cycle bursts of electrons [25–30]. In contrast to PINEM-type experiments, the resulting attosecond pulse train is formed right at the source, not downstream at a certain drift distance. However, the sub-optical-cycle bursts retain their attosecond temporal profile only at a short range from the emitter, for example in nanometer vacuum gap devices [31, 32] or in a sub-nanometer scanning tunneling microscope junction [33]. The underlying reason is that short bursts in time are accompanied by a broad energy spectrum due to Heisenberg’s time–energy uncertainty relation. This leads to strong matter-wave dispersion effects and to the inevitable stretching of the emitted electron pulses for large propagation distances, destroying the temporal fingerprint of the sub-optical-cycle emission process. Using a numerical solution of the time-dependent Schrödinger

equation (TDSE) and a classical trajectory model, we show that electron pulse trains emitted from a metal nanotip can retain their sub-optical-cycle temporal profile in a realistic experimental scenario. In PPM, laser-triggered metal nanotips serving as electron point sources enable spatiotemporal studies of charge dynamics with a resolution down to 25 fs and 20 nm [18, 34–37]. Here, an electron beam with a kinetic energy below 200 eV irradiates a sample placed at a short distance on the order of $1 \mu\text{m}$ from the tip. A distant screen captures the resulting PPM image with high magnification. As we will show, the short tip-sample distance, the rapid acceleration of the electrons toward the sample in low-energy PPM and a sufficiently large optical cycle duration are the key for retaining the temporal fingerprint of the tunneling photoemission process at the sample.

2. PPM setup and theoretical methods

In our study, we investigate electron emission and propagation from source to sample in a typical tip-sample setup for PPM, depicted in figure 1. A metal nanotip made from tungsten is irradiated by femtosecond laser pulses that induce an optical near-field at the apex of the tip [38]. The strong near-field causes the emission of a sub-optical-cycle electron burst once per laser cycle by tunneling photoemission. Propagation of the electron wavepacket pulse train to the nearby sample leads to matter-wave dispersion and broadening, affecting the its temporal shape. We consider laser pulses with two wavelengths employed in nanotip experiments, 830 nm (Ti:sapphire laser system, cf [25, 26]) and 1550 nm (Erbium fiber laser system, cf [39]). In our typical PPM setup, the tip apex radius of curvature is $R = 10$ nm, the tip-sample distance is $d = 1000$ nm and the tip-sample voltage is $U_{\text{DC}} = 50$ V.

In order to study the generation and propagation of the electron wavepacket pulse train, we employ a fully quantum-mechanical model and a classical trajectory model. In the following, we detail these two methods.

Figure 2. Sub-optical-cycle photoemission and electron propagation to the sample. (a) Enhanced electric field and time-dependent probability current at $z = 0.5$ nm for the 830 nm field. When the electric field is negative, sub-optical-cycle bursts are emitted. The slight time shift between electric field waveform and emission current peaks is due to the 0.5 nm propagation distance. Time zero ($t = 0$) coincides with the peak of the electric field. (b) The same for the 1550 nm field. (c) The color plot shows the probability density change for the 1550 nm field in logarithmic scale. The electron pulse train experiences rapid acceleration close to the tip. The pulse train structure is visible throughout.

2.1. Quantum-mechanical model

In order to simulate the emission and propagation of electrons fully quantum-mechanically, we perform a numerical integration of the TDSE. Electron spectra obtained from such TDSE calculations are in excellent agreement with experimental results of nanotip photoemission [26, 40]. We consider a single active electron propagating in one spatial dimension, the tip’s symmetry axis z . We use atomic units for all equations ($\hbar = e = m = 1$). The metal half-space ($z < 0$) is modeled by a potential well with depth $E_F + W$ (Fermi energy $E_F = 9$ eV, workfunction $W = 4.5$ eV). In the vacuum half-space ($z > 0$), we take into account the image charge potential $V_{im}(z) = -1/(4z)$, which attracts an emitted electron back to the metal surface. The initial state is confined to the potential well and possesses the initial energy E_i . We then slowly switch on the static on-axis potential between the nanotip with prolate-spheroidal shape and a flat conductive sample, which is of the form [41]

$$V_{DC} = -U_{DC} \frac{\ln \left[\frac{1+(d-z-R/4)/(d+R/4)}{1-(d-z-R/4)/(d+R/4)} \right]}{\ln \left(\frac{1-\eta_1}{1+\eta_1} \right)}. \quad (1)$$

Here we choose $\eta_1 = 0.995$, corresponding to the tip radius $R = 10$ nm (see figure 1(b) for a plot of equation (1)). The corresponding static field strength at the tip apex is 1.67 V nm^{-1} , which is below the threshold for significant field emission around 2 V nm^{-1} . After switching on the static potential, we expose the wavefunction to an optical near-field with a cosine-square envelope function, given by

$$E_{NF}(z, t) = \xi(z)E_0 \cos^2 \left(\frac{\omega t}{2N} \right) \cos \omega t, \quad (2)$$

where E_0 is the peak electric field, ω the center frequency and N the total number of cycles comprising the pulse. $\xi(z)$ is the near-field enhancement factor which decays into the vacuum space. Following [42], we describe the spatial decay by an exponential function

$$\xi(z) = 1 + (\xi_0 - 1) \exp(-z/d_\xi), \quad (3)$$

where ξ_0 is the field enhancement factor at the tip’s surface and d_ξ the $1/e$ decay constant. Motivated by classical electrodynamics calculations of nanotip field enhancement [38, 43], we choose $\xi_0 = 5$ and $d_\xi \approx 0.8R$ for both wavelengths (see figure 1(b) for a rendition of $\xi(z)$). We assume that the field

Figure 3. Arrival probability at the sample. (a) 830 nm field, single initial state at the Fermi level. (b) The same for the 1550 nm field. In both cases, the fingerprint of the tunneling emission process is clearly visible, enabling sub-optical-cycle interactions with the sample. (c) 830 nm field, incoherent sum of the arrival probability for all initial states at and below the Fermi level. The sub-optical-cycle burst structure is washed out. (d) The same for the 1550 nm field. The sub-optical-cycle burst structure remains clearly visible.

vanishes inside the metal half-space due to perfect screening. The resulting potential due to the near-field is given by

$$V_{\text{NF}}(z, t) = \int_0^z E_{\text{NF}}(z', t) dz'. \quad (4)$$

Finally, we obtain the time-dependent wavefunction $\psi(z, t)$ by solving the TDSE using the Crank–Nicolson method and determine the arrival time distribution at the sample plane. We also calculate the energy spectrum from the Fourier transformation of the wavefunction at the sample.

2.2. Classical trajectory model

In order to gain more insight into the underlying physics, we use a simple classical trajectory model. We assume a sub-optical-cycle electron emission probability distribution in order to mimick tunneling photoemission driven by five subsequent cycles of the light fields. It is described by the sum of Gaussian functions

$$P_{\text{emission}}(t) = \sum_{n=-2}^2 \exp \left[-\frac{(t - nT_{\text{opt}})^2}{2t_{\text{emission}}} \right], \quad (5)$$

where $n \in \{-2, -1, 0, 1, 2\}$ is the cycle number, $T_{\text{opt}} = 2\pi/\omega$ is the optical cycle duration and $t_{\text{emission}} = T_{\text{opt}}/6$ is the duration of each sub-optical-cycle electron burst. We model the corresponding electron energy spectrum through its Fourier transform up to a constant factor,

$$P_{\text{spectrum}}(E_{\text{kin}}) = \left| \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \sqrt{P(t)} \exp[i(E_{\text{kin}} - E_{\text{kin,offset}})t] dt \right|^2, \quad (6)$$

where E_{kin} is the kinetic energy and $E_{\text{kin,offset}} > 0$ is an initial energy offset. The energy spectrum consists of a comb of peaks separated by the photon energy of the light field, which reflects the periodicity of the electron bursts. We propagate the classical joint energy–time electron distribution given by equations (5) and (6) in the static tip-sample potential using the Runge–Kutta–Fehlberg method and record the corresponding arrival time distribution.

3. Results

We consider two cases, an 830 nm light pulse with a full-width half-maximum (FWHM) intensity duration of 16.1 fs

($N = 16$) and an enhanced near-field intensity of $1.2 \times 10^{13} \text{ W cm}^{-2}$, and a 1550 nm light pulse with an FWHM intensity duration of 30 fs ($N = 16$) and an enhanced near-field intensity of $8 \times 10^{12} \text{ W cm}^{-2}$ (see upper panels of figures 2(a) and (b)). The corresponding Keldysh parameters [44] are 1.7 and 1.1, respectively, which places the emission process in the transition regime between the multiphoton and tunneling limits of photoemission [23, 24].

3.1. Quantum-mechanical model

For the TDSE calculations, we first consider an initial wavefunction at the Fermi energy, $E_i = E_F$, and its interactions with the light pulses. We then propagate the wavefunction and analyze the resulting emission and propagation. The lower panels of figures 2(a) and (b) show the induced time-dependent probability current measured at $z = 0.5 \text{ nm}$. For both fields, we find that the current is confined to sub-optical-cycle bursts once per field cycle, confirming that the notion of tunneling is still valid in the transition regime [45]. When the optical near-field is negative, it can strongly bend down the potential barrier, enabling electrons to tunnel out in sub-optical-cycle bursts. An electron wavepacket pulse train is emitted into the vacuum half-space. Figures 2(a) and (b) also shows weaker currents in negative direction, which are due to the oscillatory motion of the electrons in the near-field. The duration of the strongest burst is about 600 as and 1.2 fs for the 830 nm field and the 1550 nm field, respectively. The total current in positive direction outweighs the total current in negative direction by a factor of 4.4 and 4.8 for the 830 nm field and the 1550 nm field, respectively.

Next, we track the motion of the emitted pulse train in the optical near-field and the static tip-sample potential. Figure 2(c) shows the probability density change $|\psi(z, t)|^2 - |\psi_0(z)|^2$ for the 1550 nm case, where $\psi_0(z)$ is the initial wavefunction. As expected from the static tip-sample potential shown in figure 1(b), the pulse train experiences rapid acceleration in the vicinity of the tip surface, keeping the pulse train together and conserving its temporal structure quite well. After about 280 fs from the center of the light pulses, the pulse train reaches the sample plane. Faster electron wavepacket components, such as rescattered electrons [26], reach the sample plane earlier, but have only minuscule amplitude and do not contribute significantly.

Figure 4. Arrival probabilities and energy spectra for different initial states. (a) Arrival probability as a function of initial energy shift with respect to the Fermi energy for the 830 nm field. (b) Corresponding energy spectrum. (c) and (d) Show the same for the 1550 nm field.

Figure 5. Arrival time distributions obtained with the classical trajectory model. (a) 830 nm case. (b) 1550 nm case. The two circles mark the maximum *A* and the minimum *B*, which we use for determining the sub-optical-cycle contrast.

Figures 3(a) and (b) shows the arrival probability of the wavefunction at the sample plane. We find that the sub-optical-cycle temporal fingerprint is still visible in both cases when the wavefunction arrives at the sample. The periodicity of the bursts reflects the optical cycle duration, though not perfectly due to the matter-wave dispersion effects. The temporal contrast of the bursts has significantly deteriorated compared to the point of emission. However, the overall modulation of the wavefunction turns out to be robust and can be employed for sub-optical-cycle interactions with the sample.

Up to now, we have only considered a single initial state at the Fermi energy. For a realistic study, we also calculate the TDSE wavefunction propagation for initial states up to 1.5 eV below E_F . In the TDSE approach, experimental energy spectra are well reproduced by an *incoherent* sum over the TDSE energy spectra from all possible initial states, weighted by the density of states [40]. Here we perform the incoherent sum over the arrival probability at the sample plane in order to account for the contribution of all initial states. Figure 3(c) shows that this summation inevitably causes a complete washing out of the sub-optical-cycle temporal fingerprint for the 830 nm case. The 1550 nm case, however, still exhibits the fingerprint with a decreased contrast (see figure 3(d)).

In order to gain more insight into the underlying physics, we take a closer look at the arrival probabilities and the electron energy spectra corresponding to each initial state. Figure 4

displays these quantities as a function of the initial energy shift with respect to the Fermi energy. A strong dependence on the initial state can be observed both in the time and in the energy domain for both fields. We emphasize that the arrival probability corresponding to each initial state still carries the temporal fingerprint. However, the overall time delay varies and leads to the blurring effect upon summation for the 800 nm field. Here the time shift of the arrival probability for an initial energy shift equal to the photon energy (1.49 eV) amounts to about 8 fs and is much larger than the optical cycle duration (2.8 fs), causing the strong blurring effect. This is in stark contrast to the 1550 nm case, which shows the sub-optical-cycle behavior. The time shift of the arrival probability for an initial energy shift equal to the photon energy (0.80 eV) amounts to about 4 fs and is slightly less than the optical cycle duration (5.3 fs). In conjunction with the steeply decreasing overall emission probability, the sub-optical-cycle fingerprint is retained. This finding highlights the importance of the optical cycle duration, which needs to be sufficiently large.

3.2. Classical trajectory model

Our observations are in qualitative agreement with the simple classical trajectory model. In order to introduce the initial state energy dependence, we vary the initial energy offset $E_{\text{kin,offset}}$ by about half of the photon energy, which corresponds to 0.75 eV and 0.375 eV for the 830 nm field

Figure 6. Sub-optical-cycle contrast according to the classical trajectory model. (a) Contrast as a function of acceleration voltage and tip-sample distance for the 830 nm case. (b) The same for the 1550 nm case.

and the 1550 nm field, respectively. We determine the corresponding arrival time distributions and perform the summation. Figure 5 shows the resulting arrival time distributions for both cases. The 830 nm result shows strong blurring, while the 1550 nm result clearly resembles the initial sub-optical-cycle emission.

The classical trajectory model with its low computational cost also allows us to explore the matter-wave dispersion effects for a large range of acceleration voltages and tip-sample distances. As a measure of the severity of the dispersion effects and the visibility of sub-optical-cycle modulations at the sample plane, we define the sub-optical-cycle contrast as $C = (A - B)/(A + B)$, where A is the maximum of the arrival probability and B is the minimum of the arrival probability right next to it (see figure 5(b) for an illustration). Figure 6 shows C as a function of acceleration voltage and tip-sample distance for both fields. The radius of curvature of the tip is kept constant, $R = 10$ nm. In general, we find that dispersion is harmful to the contrast for low voltages and long propagation distances, as expected. The 1550 nm field shows better contrast behavior due to the larger optical cycle duration. Although it seems desirable to work with higher acceleration voltages according to these plots, a further limiting factor must be taken into account, namely the onset of field emission at a static field strength of about 2 V nm^{-1} . Field emission is not pulsed and does not enable time-resolved measurements. In order to suppress field emission, the voltage must be kept sufficiently low. For the parameters we chose in the previous part ($U_{\text{DC}} = 50 \text{ V}$, $d = 1000 \text{ nm}$), we obtain a static field strength of 1.67 V nm^{-1} , hence this requirement is fulfilled.

4. Robustness of the approach

In the previous part, we have considered a fixed set of parameters for peak intensity, field enhancement factor and tip radius. For an experimental realization of our approach, it is helpful to verify its robustness by varying these parameters. In the following, we will consider such variations for the 1550 nm field using our models. Unless otherwise noted, we are using

the same parameters as in the previous part ($U_{\text{DC}} = 50 \text{ V}$, $d = 1000 \text{ nm}$, $R = 10 \text{ nm}$, $\eta_1 = 0.995$, $\xi_0 = 5$, peak intensity $8 \times 10^{12} \text{ W cm}^{-2}$). Moreover, we will discuss experimental limitations which are not captured by our models, such as space-charge repulsion.

Tip shape. The amount of initial static field acceleration of the emitted electrons near the tip is determined by the tip shape. Figure 7(a) shows the sub-optical-cycle contrast C at the sample plane as function of tip radius R , varied from 10 to 50 nm in accordance with a typical experiment [43]. In this calculation we employ the classical trajectory model. We find that increasing the tip radius does not lead to an unacceptable deterioration of the contrast below a threshold value of 0.5, but rather to an increase for large tip radii. Changing the tip radius does not lead to a loss of the sub-optical-cycle fingerprint.

Field enhancement factor. The optical near-field enhancement is linked to the tip shape and the wavelength of the light. The sharper the tip is, the stronger the field enhancement becomes [38, 43, 46]. Moreover, the enhancement for metal nanotips generally increases with wavelength in the infrared regime [43]. One might simply increase the wavelength more, for example, by employing ultrashort pulses at 1800 nm [47] or at 2400 nm [48], but this will change the optical cycle duration and the periodicity of the sub-optical-cycle bursts. However, we find that the magnitude of the field enhancement does not play a significant role in the process. In order to assess the influence of the field enhancement on the sub-optical-cycle modulation, we vary the enhancement factor ξ_0 in our quantum-mechanical model between 3 and 7 while keeping the near-field's peak electric field constant. We find no significant impact on the resulting arrival probability (see figure 7(b)).

Light polarization. In our study, we assume that the optical near-field is linearly polarized along the tip's symmetry axis. This choice is in agreement with most nanotip experiments (see [23] for a review) where the incident laser field was polarized in the same way. Such a configuration ensures maximum field enhancement compared to other polarization configurations [38].

Figure 7. Robustness with respect to experimental parameters for the 1550 nm field. (a) Sub-optical-cycle contrast as a function of tip radius, calculated with the classical trajectory model. (b) Arrival probability as a function of time and field enhancement factor, determined from the quantum model. (c) Emission rate as a function of the Keldysh parameter in a double-logarithmic plot (quantum model). Smaller Keldysh parameters correspond to higher peak electric fields. (d) Arrival probability as a function of time and Keldysh parameter (quantum model). We normalized the arrival probability for each Keldysh parameter separately in order to increase the visibility of the plot. (e) Arrival probability as a function of time and pulse duration (quantum model).

Peak intensity. Photoemission from metal nanotips is a nonlinear process, resulting in a strong dependence of the emission rate on intensity [23, 24]. In the framework of the Keldysh theory [44], the Keldysh parameter that governs the photoemission mechanism is defined as $\gamma = \sqrt{W/(2U_p)}$. Here $U_p = \xi_0^2 E_0^2 / (4\omega^2)$ is the ponderomotive energy in the near-field, which is directly proportional to the peak intensity. Using our quantum-mechanical model, we calculate the emission rate as a function of γ (see figure 7(c) for a double-logarithmic plot of the rate). While the nonlinear scaling is apparent, it is not *a priori* clear if the sub-optical-cycle modulation is present. The color plot in figure 7(d) shows the arrival probability as a function of γ . For $\gamma > 1$, the periodicity and the sub-optical-cycle fingerprint remain more or less undisturbed, which is not surprising because even for $\gamma \sim 3$, sub-optical-cycle emission is expected [26, 45]. For $\gamma < 1$, more peaks with a different periodicity appear at earlier times. For a clean electron pulse train with a single dominant periodicity, operation at $\gamma < 1$ should therefore be avoided.

Pulse duration. Decreasing the pulse duration in order to reach the few-cycle regime has the potential to enable control of the photoemission using the carrier-envelope phase (CEP). Such control has been demonstrated at metal nanotips and can restrict the emission to a single or double burst, depending on the CEP [26, 28]. In order to assess the influence of the pulse duration, we varied the FWHM duration between 7.5 and 30 fs and calculated the arrival probability using the quantum-mechanical model. We find that the sub-optical-cycle

fingerprint is visible throughout as the number of bursts is reduced. However, the periodicity increases and reaches about 8.5 fs at 7.5 fs pulse duration, which is significantly larger than 5.3 fs, the optical cycle duration at 1550 nm. We recommend operation of nanotip with a large number of cycles for obtaining a clean electron pulse train with well-defined periodicity.

Electron density and space-charge repulsion. Our models are describing the dynamics of a single electron and do not capture multi-electron effects, such as space-charge repulsion between multiple electrons after they are emitted. Such effects are known to be harmful for coherent wavepacket propagation and hence could potentially destroy the sub-optical-cycle fingerprint, as shown in a PINEM-like experiment carried out at a thin metallic membrane [49]. A straightforward solution to avoid space-charge repulsion effects is to tune the laser intensity so that on average only one electron is emitted. An experimental realization of nanotip photoemission triggered by a 1550 nm laser field was reported by Förster *et al* [39]. Studying emission from a tungsten tip ($R = 10$ nm), the authors reported about 10^{-3} electrons per laser pulse for an estimated Keldysh parameter $\gamma \sim 3$. According to our simulations, a clear sub-optical-cycle fingerprint is expected for $\gamma \sim 3$ (see figure 7(d)). Extrapolating the experimental result to $\gamma \sim 1$ using our calculations from figure 7(c) yields an estimate of one electron per pulse, which corresponds to the desired regime. The single-electron operation can be verified in an experiment by measuring the total current drawn from the tip using a sensitive current preamplifier. At a laser pulse

repetition rate of 80 MHz, we expect an average current of 13 pA. This current is much lower than the nA-level currents used in low-energy electron holography experiments for imaging biomolecules, where no damage is exerted [50].

Thermal load on the tip. High-repetition laser sources, such as oscillators, operate in the MHz regime. This can lead to a significant thermal load on the nanotip. However, experimental investigations [26, 39, 43, 51] show that metal nanotips made from tungsten or gold can withstand an oscillator repetition rate of 80 MHz when operated close to $\gamma \sim 1$. A systematic study of heat conductivity in the context of nanotip photoemission supports this notion [52].

5. Conclusion and outlook

In conclusion, we have demonstrated through a quantum-mechanical and a classical model that sub-optical-cycle electron pulse trains produced by mid-infrared-driven tunneling photoemission from a metal nanotip retain the temporal fingerprint of the emission process after propagation to a nearby sample. Rapid acceleration of the electrons toward the sample, short propagation distances and a sufficiently large optical cycle duration of the light field lead to the formation of a strongly modulated arrival probability distribution at the sample, enabling sub-optical-cycle interactions between the electron pulse train and a sample in a typical PPM setup.

Our approach for producing electron pulse trains represents a simple and practical alternative to the optical manipulation of free-space electron beams in SEMs and TEMs. Within the PPM approach, no electron optics is necessary as the static field acceleration and the magnification are solely defined by the tip-sample-screen geometry. Moreover, the kinetic energies of the electrons arriving at the sample are significantly lower than those in SEMs or TEMs, enabling studies of ultrafast interactions of slow electrons with matter. At such low energies the non-recoil approximation of electron-matter interaction is expected to break down, manifesting itself in transverse electron momentum shifts [13, 19]. Another advantage of using slow electrons is low damage to sensitive samples, such as biomolecules [50]. Lastly, electron pulses from nanotips carry a high degree of spatial coherence and can record ultrafast holographic snapshots of their interactions with a sample [37, 53, 54]. We expect that ultrafast low-energy electron holography with attosecond electron pulse trains generated directly at the nanotip will enable spatio-temporal studies of charge dynamics with unprecedented resolution.

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Data availability statement

The data that support the findings of this study are available upon reasonable request from the authors.

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References

- [1] Corkum P B and Krausz F 2007 Attosecond science *Nat. Phys.* **3** 381–7
- [2] Calegari F, Sansone G, Stagira S, Vozzi C and Nisoli M 2016 Advances in attosecond science *J. Phys. B: At. Mol. Opt. Phys.* **49** 062001
- [3] Barwick B, Flannigan D J and Zewail A H 2009 Photon-induced near-field electron microscopy *Nature* **462** 902–6
- [4] Breuer J and Hommelhoff P 2013 Laser-based acceleration of nonrelativistic electrons at a dielectric structure *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **111** 134803
- [5] Peralta E A *et al* 2013 Demonstration of electron acceleration in a laser-driven dielectric microstructure *Nature* **503** 91–4
- [6] Feist A, Echtenkamp K E, Schauss J, Yalunin S V, Schäfer S and Ropers C 2015 Quantum coherent optical phase modulation in an ultrafast transmission electron microscope *Nature* **521** 200–3
- [7] Echtenkamp K E, Feist A, Schäfer S and Ropers C 2016 Ramsey-type phase control of free-electron beams *Nat. Phys.* **12** 1000–4
- [8] Priebe K E, Rathje C, Yalunin S V, Hohage T, Feist A, Schäfer S and Ropers C 2017 Attosecond electron pulse trains and quantum state reconstruction in ultrafast transmission electron microscopy *Nat. Photon.* **11** 793–7
- [9] Schönenberger N, Mittelbach A, Yousefi P, McNeur J, Niedermayer U and Hommelhoff P 2019 Generation and characterization of attosecond microbunched electron pulse trains via dielectric laser acceleration *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **123** 264803
- [10] Morimoto Y and Baum P 2018 Diffraction and microscopy with attosecond electron pulse trains *Nat. Phys.* **14** 252–6
- [11] García de Abajo F J 2010 Optical excitations in electron microscopy *Rev. Mod. Phys.* **82** 209–75
- [12] Hohenester U 2020 *Nano and Quantum Optics* (Berlin: Springer)
- [13] García de Abajo F J and Di Giulio V 2021 Optical excitations with electron beams: challenges and opportunities *ACS Photonics* **8** 945–74
- [14] Gover A and Yariv A 2020 Free-electron-bound-electron resonant interaction *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **124** 064801
- [15] Karnieli A, Rivera N, Arie A and Kaminer I 2021 Superradiance and subradiance due to quantum interference of entangled free electrons *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **127** 060403
- [16] Ruimy R, Gorkach A, Mechel C, Rivera N and Kaminer I 2021 Toward atomic-resolution quantum measurements with coherently shaped free electrons *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **126** 233403
- [17] Shiloh R, Chlouba T and Hommelhoff P 2021 Quantum-coherent light-electron interaction in an SEM (arXiv:2110.00764)
- [18] Vogelsang J, Hergert G, Wang D, Groß P and Lienau C 2018 Observing charge separation in nanoantennas via ultrafast point-projection electron microscopy *Light Sci. Appl.* **7** 55
- [19] Talebi N 2020 Strong interaction of slow electrons with near-field light visited from first principles *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **125** 080401

- [20] Morimoto Y and Baum P 2020 Single-cycle optical control of beam electrons *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **125** 193202
- [21] Kozák M, Eckstein T, Schönenberger N and Hommelhoff P 2018 Inelastic ponderomotive scattering of electrons at a high-intensity optical travelling wave in vacuum *Nat. Phys.* **14** 121–5
- [22] Kozák M, Schönenberger N and Hommelhoff P 2018 Ponderomotive generation and detection of attosecond free-electron pulse trains *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **120** 103203
- [23] Krüger M, Lemell C, Wachter G, Burgdörfer J and Hommelhoff P 2018 Attosecond physics phenomena at nanometric tips *J. Phys. B: At. Mol. Opt. Phys.* **51** 172001
- [24] Dombi P *et al* 2020 Strong-field nano-optics *Rev. Mod. Phys.* **92** 025003
- [25] Bormann R, Gulde M, Weismann A, Yalunin S V and Ropers C 2010 Tip-enhanced strong-field photoemission *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **105** 147601
- [26] Krüger M, Schenk M and Hommelhoff P 2011 Attosecond control of electrons emitted from a nanoscale metal tip *Nature* **475** 78–81
- [27] Herink G, Solli D R, Gulde M and Ropers C 2012 Field-driven photoemission from nanostructures quenches the quiver motion *Nature* **483** 190–3
- [28] Piglosiewicz B, Schmidt S, Park D J, Vogelsang J, Groß P, Manzoni C, Farinello P, Cerullo G and Lienau C 2014 Carrier-envelope phase effects on the strong-field photoemission of electrons from metallic nanostructures *Nat. Photon.* **8** 37–42
- [29] Rybka T, Ludwig M, Schmalz M F, Knittel V, Brida D and Leitenstorfer A 2016 Sub-cycle optical phase control of nanotunnelling in the single-electron regime *Nat. Photon.* **10** 667–70
- [30] Putnam W P, Hobbs R G, Keathley P D, Berggren K K and Kärtner F X 2017 Optical-field-controlled photoemission from plasmonic nanoparticles *Nat. Phys.* **13** 335–9
- [31] Ludwig M, Aguirregabiria G, Ritzkowski F, Rybka T, Marinica D C, Aizpurua J, Borisov A G, Leitenstorfer A and Brida D 2020 Sub-femtosecond electron transport in a nanoscale gap *Nat. Phys.* **16** 341–5
- [32] Bionta M R, Ritzkowski F, Turchetti M, Yang Y, Cattozzo M, Putnam W P, Kärtner F X, Berggren K K and Keathley P D 2021 On-chip sampling of optical fields with attosecond resolution *Nat. Photon.* **15** 456–60
- [33] Garg M and Kern K 2020 Attosecond coherent manipulation of electrons in tunneling microscopy *Science* **367** 411–5
- [34] Quinonez E, Handali J and Barwick B 2013 Femtosecond photoelectron point projection microscope *Rev. Sci. Instrum.* **84** 103710
- [35] Müller M, Paarmann A and Ernstorfer R 2015 Femtosecond electrons probing currents and atomic structure in nanomaterials *Nat. Commun.* **5** 5292
- [36] Müller M, Kravtsov V, Paarmann A, Raschke M B and Ernstorfer R 2016 Nanofocused plasmon-driven sub-10 fs electron point source *ACS Photonics* **3** 611–9
- [37] Vogelsang J, Talebi N, Hergert G, Wöste A, Groß P, Hartschuh A and Lienau C 2018 Plasmonic-nanofocusing-based electron holography *ACS Photonics* **5** 3584–93
- [38] Thomas S, Wachter G, Lemell C, Burgdörfer J and Hommelhoff P 2015 Large optical field enhancement for nanotips with large opening angles *New J. Phys.* **17** 063010
- [39] Förster M, Paschen T, Krüger M, Lemell C, Wachter G, Libisch F, Madlener T, Burgdörfer J and Hommelhoff P 2016 Two-color coherent control of femtosecond above-threshold photoemission from a tungsten nanotip *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **117** 217601
- [40] Yalunin S V, Herink G, Solli D R, Krüger M, Hommelhoff P, Diehn M, Munk A and Ropers C 2013 Field localization and rescattering in tip-enhanced photoemission *Ann. Phys., Lpz.* **525** L12–8
- [41] Pan L H, Sullivan T E, Peridier V J, Cutler P H and Miskovsky N M 1994 Three-dimensional electrostatic potential, and potential-energy barrier, near a tip-base junction *Appl. Phys. Lett.* **65** 2151–3
- [42] Seiffert L, Paschen T, Hommelhoff P and Fennel T 2018 High-order above-threshold photoemission from nanotips controlled with two-color laser fields *J. Phys. B: At. Mol. Opt. Phys.* **51** 134001
- [43] Thomas S, Krüger M, Förster M, Schenk M and Hommelhoff P 2013 Probing of optical near-fields by electron rescattering on the 1 nm scale *Nano Lett.* **13** 4790–4
- [44] Keldysh L V 1965 Ionization in the field of a strong electromagnetic wave *Sov. Phys. JETP* **20** 1307–14
- [45] Yudin G L and Ivanov M Y 2001 Nonadiabatic tunnel ionization: looking inside a laser cycle *Phys. Rev. A* **64** 013409
- [46] Krüger M, Thomas S, Förster M and Hommelhoff P 2014 Self-probing of metal nanotips by rescattered electrons reveals the nano-optical near-field *J. Phys. B: At. Mol. Opt. Phys.* **47** 124022
- [47] Homann C, Bradler M, Förster M, Hommelhoff P and Riedle E 2012 Carrier-envelope phase stable sub-two-cycle pulses tunable around 1.8 μm at 100 kHz *Opt. Lett.* **37** 1673–5
- [48] Vasilyev S *et al* 2021 Kerr-lens mode-locked Cr:ZnS oscillator reaches the spectral span of an optical octave *Opt. Express* **29** 2458–65
- [49] Kirchner F O, Gliserin A, Krausz F and Baum P 2014 Laser streaking of free electrons at 25 keV *Nat. Photon.* **8** 52–7
- [50] Longchamp J-N, Rauschenbach S, Abb S, Escher C, Latychevskaia T, Kern K and Fink H-W 2017 Imaging proteins at the single-molecule level *Proc. Natl Acad. Sci. USA* **114** 1474–9
- [51] Dienstbier P, Paschen T and Hommelhoff P 2021 Coherent control at gold needle tips approaching the strong-field regime *Nanophotonics* **10** 3717–21
- [52] Kealhofer C, Foreman S M, Gerlich S and Kasevich M A 2012 Ultrafast laser-triggered emission from hafnium carbide tips *Phys. Rev. B* **86** 035405
- [53] Ehberger D, Hammer J, Eisele M, Krüger M, Noe J, Högele A and Hommelhoff P 2015 Highly coherent electron beam from a laser-triggered tungsten needle tip *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **114** 227601
- [54] Meier S, Higuchi T, Nutz M, Högele A and Hommelhoff P 2018 High spatial coherence in multiphoton-photoemitted electron beams *Appl. Phys. Lett.* **113** 143101